

Electrometric Studies on the Composition and Stability Constants of Nickel- β Mercapto-propionic Acid Complexes

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Potentiometric and Conductometric studies of the Nickel- β -Mercapto-propionic acid system in aqueous 0.1 $MKNO_3$ indicate the presence of two complexes; one light brown 1:1, predominating at pH 7.0-7.5 and another deep brown 1:2 in the pH range 8.0-9.5. The stability constants of these complexes have been determined at three different temperatures by applying Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method. The log K values (final) for 1:1 and 1:2 complexes, computed by alternative methods at 20, 30 and 40°, have been found to be 5.39 ± 0.07 , 5.49 ± 0.09 , 5.59 ± 0.03 and 5.19 ± 0.10 , 5.25 ± 0.11 , and 5.34 ± 0.11 respectively. The values of overall changes in ΔG , ΔH and ΔS accompanying the reaction have also been evaluated at 30° and found to be -14.87 K-cal/mole, -7.03 K-cal/mole and $+25.87$ cal/deg. respectively.

Mercapto-acids and other sulphydryl compounds are strong complexing agents, owing to the presence of one or more -SH group for coordination with metal ions, and hence several workers have focussed their interest on the complexation of these compounds with various metals.¹⁻⁷ In our earlier publications⁸⁻¹¹, investigations on the composition stability constants and thermodynamic functions of the complexes of metals such as Ag^+ , Ni^{++} , Zn^{++} and Tl (I) with Thiomalic acid has been reported. It was considered of interest to extend similar investigations on the complexation of β -Mercapto-propionic acid (referred to herein as MPA) with Nickel (II). The literature is, however, silent on the study of Ni^{2+} -MPA system and hence the current study has been undertaken. This contribution describes a potentiometric and conductometric study of Ni^{2+} -MPA system which involved the computation of successive stability constants by alternative methods (correction term method, convergence formulas of successive approximations, least square treatment), the effect of temperature variation on the stabilities of complexes and the determination of overall changes in free energy, enthalpy and entropy accompanying the reaction.

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EXPERIMENTAL

β -Mercapto-propionic acid (99.1%, Evan's Chemetics, Inc., New York) and Anala-R (B.D.H.) reagents NiSO_4 , KNO_3 , NaOH , etc., were used and their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled air free conductivity water. Freshly prepared solutions were always used with a view to avoiding the effects of ageing and hydrolysis. Nickel content in Nickel sulphate solution was estimated as Nickel-Dimethylglyoximate.

$p\text{H}$ -measurements were made on a Cambridge bench pattern (null deflection type) $p\text{H}$ -meter. A wide range glass electrode calibrated frequently by using several solutions 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} M HClO_4 with ionic strength 0.1 M (obtained by addition of NaClO_4), was used in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell by low resistance salt bridge. Thus the readings gave immediately concentrations and not activities of H^+ . Before and after each series of measurements, a calibration was made. Though the meter can measure 0.01 unit of $p\text{H}$, it is supposed that with the error inherent in calibration, the ultimate error is ± 0.02 $p\text{H}$ unit. All the $p\text{H}$ titrations were carried out in aqueous 0.1 M KNO_3 . During the experiments, a CO_2 free nitrogen (presaturated with 0.1 M KNO_3) atmosphere was maintained above the solution and electromagnetic stirring was used. The temperature was controlled by an electrically maintained thermostat.

The conductance measurements were carried out by means of an electronic eye type conductometer (LBR, WTW, Germany).

The experimental procedure involved a series of $p\text{H}$ and conductometric titrations of β -Mercapto-propionic acid with standard NaOH in the absence and presence of Ni^{2+} at various ligand to metal ratios. Calvin and Melchior's¹² extension of Bjerrum's¹³ method was used to calculate the stability constants of the complexes formed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stoichiometry: The stoichiometry of the reaction between Ni^{2+} and β -Mercapto-propionic acid was determined by potentiometric and conductometric titrations of mixtures of reactants in various ratios against standard alkali.

Figure 1, represents the $p\text{H}$ and conductometric titrations of solutions 3.33×10^{-3} M in MPA (curves 1 and 5), 3.33×10^{-3} M in MPA and 3.33×10^{-3} M in NiSO_4 (curves 2 and 6), and 3.33×10^{-3} M in MPA and 1.66×10^{-3} M in NiSO_4 (curves 3 and 7) and 3.33×10^{-3} M in MPA and 1.11×10^{-3} M in NiSO_4 (curve 4) with 0.1 M NaOH . The abscissa represents the moles of NaOH added per mole of ligand 'a'.

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The appearance of only one inflection (fig. 1, curve 1) after one mole of base per mole of ligand has been added corresponds to the neutralisation of the single carboxyl hydrogen. Hence if free MPA, having two replaceable hydrogen ions is denoted as H_2SA , the reaction

Fig. 1. Potentiometric (curves 1-4) and conductometric (curves 5-7) titrations of MPA in the absence and presence of Ni^{2+} with 0.1 M NaOH.

Curves 1 and 5. $3.33 \times 10^{-3}M$ MPA.

Curves 2 and 4. $3.33 \times 10^{-3}M$ MPA + $3.33 \times 10^{-3}M$ $NiSO_4$.

Curves 3 and 7. $3.33 \times 10^{-3}M$ MPA + $1.66 \times 10^{-3}M$ $NiSO_4$.

Curve 4. $3.33 \times 10^{-3}M$ MPA.

between a interval of 0-1 may be represented by the equation.

The absence of inflection at $a = 2$ indicates that the second proton (sulphydryl) of MPA is not titrated under the experimental conditions.

The addition of equimolar concentration of Ni^{2+} (fig. 1, curve 2), greatly alters the shape of the free ligand titration curve as a result of the complex formation and consequently a considerable shift in the position of the end point is indicated. Since the extent of the proton displacement depends on the relative affinities of the ligand for hydrogen ions and the metal ions, it is obvious from the curve that the affinity of Ni^{2+} is not great enough to compete with the relatively high concentration of hydrogen ions in the pH range of 3.5-6.00 and consequently Ni Complex is not appreciably formed in this pH range. Beyond pH 6.0, the affinity of ligand for Ni^{2+} ions increases, as a result of which a considerable lowering in buffer region starts showing finally two inflections at 2 and 3 moles of NaOH per mole of ligand. The inflection at $a = 2$, suggests the formation of $NiSA$, which may be shown by the equation

Further reaction with another mole of hydroxyl ion is indicated by the fact that Ni^{2+} titration curve has an additional buffer region and a second inflection at $a = 3$. Thus the second reaction step suggests the formation of a relatively more stable higher complex $\text{Ni}(\text{SA})_2^{2-}$ as a result of the disproportionation of 1 : 1 complex with simultaneous precipitation of half of the metal ion in the form of its hydroxide in accordance with the following equation

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titrations of MPA in the absence and presence of Ni^{2+} with 0.1M NaOH at three different temperatures.

Curves 1, 3 and 5. 3.0 ml MKNO_3 + 5.0 ml M/50 MPA (Total volume 30.0 ml) at 20, 30 and 40° respectively.

Curves 2, 4 and 6. 3.0 ml MKNO_3 + 5.0 ml M/50 MPA + 1.0 ml M/50 NiSO_4 (Total volume 30.0 ml) at 20, 30 and 40° respectively.

When two moles of ligand are added to NiSO_4 (fig. 1, curve 3), the curve shows only two inflections, first at $a = 1.5$ and second at $a = 2$, which correspond to the stepwise formation of NiSA and $\text{Ni}(\text{SA})_2^{2-}$ respectively. The reaction equilibria may be expressed as

The stepwise formation of these two complexes have been further confirmed by the inflections at $a \approx 1.33$ and 1.66 (fig. 1, curve 4) even when the ratio of metal to ligand has increased to 1 : 3.

Conductometric Studies : Figure 1, curves 5, 6 and 7 represents the changes in conductance when solutions of MPA were titrated against NaOH in the absence and presence of Ni^{2+} . In such conductometric titrations where the weak acid was neutralised by a strong base, the shape of the titration curve depends on the concentration and dissociation constants of the acid. The curves show a minimum, because when NaOH is added progressively to a solution of MPA, the salt formed during the first part of the reaction tends to repress the ionisation of the acid still present so that its conductance decreases. The rising salt concentration will, however, tend to increase the conductance, owing to these opposing influences, the titration curves show a minimum. As the titration proceeds break at $a = 1$ (fig. 1, curve 5) was obtained and beyond which the graph becomes linear.

Fig. 1, curve 6, for a solution containing 1 : 1 ratio of MPA to Ni^{2+} shows two breaks at $a = 2$ and 3 corresponding to the formation of NiSA and the formation of $\text{Ni}(\text{SA})_2^{2-}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ (equations 2 and 3) respectively.

Fig. 1, curve 7, for a solution containing MPA and NiSO_4 in the ratio of 2 : 1 shows two breaks at $a = 1.5$ and $a = 2$ which confirm the formation of NiSA and $\text{Ni}(\text{SA})_2^{2-}$ respectively in accordance with the equations 4 and 5.

These results are similar to those obtained by potentiometric methods demonstrating the stepwise formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes.

It may be particularly pointed out that polynuclear complex is not formed because \bar{n} is the function $[\text{SA}^{2-}]$ only (which has been tested by obtaining measurements at various metal ion concentrations) and is independent of the total metal ion concentration.

Computation of Stability Constants : The Calvin and Melchior's¹² extension of Bjerrum's¹³ method was used to calculate, the stability constants of the complexes, from potentiometric titration data. The two successive reactions of complex formation may be represented by the following equations

The overall stability constant β is given by

$$\beta = \frac{[\text{Ni}(\text{SA})_2^{2-}]}{[\text{Ni}^{2+}][\text{SA}^{2-}]^2} = K_1 K_2 \quad (8)$$

where K_1 and K_2 are the formation constants of the reactions (6) and (7).

The procedure used for calculating the stepwise stability constants of Nickel-mercapto propionate complexes was similar to that adopted in earlier publications⁸⁻¹¹. The evaluation of \bar{n} values were made from figure 2 which represents the potentiometric titrations of MPA with standard alkali in the absence and presence of Ni^{2+} at three different temperatures. At any pH, the horizontal distances between curves 1-2, 3-4 and 5-6 (corresponding to 20, 30 and 40° respectively) measure quite accurately the additional base consumed or the

total number of SA^{2-} complexed. This number divided by total $[\text{Ni}^{2+}]$ is \bar{n} . At any $p\text{H}$, $[\text{SA}^{2-}]$ was calculated as

$$[\text{SA}^{2-}] = \frac{[\text{H}_2\text{SA}] \text{ total} - [\text{NiSA}] - 2[\text{Ni}(\text{SA})_2^{2-}]}{\frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_{a_1}K_{a_2}} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_{a_2}} + 1} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 3. Plot of \bar{n} as a function of $-\log [\text{SA}^{2-}]$ at three different temperatures.

Curve-1 at 20° .

Curve-2 at 30° .

Curve-3 at 40° .

where K_{a_1} ($pK_{a_1} = 4.38$) and K_{a_2} ($pK_{a_2} = 10.38$) are the first and second dissociation constants of the acid. All quantities in equation (9) are known and thus a series of \bar{n} and $[\text{SA}^{2-}]$ values at various $p\text{H}$ were obtained at different temperatures and formation curves were plotted (figure 3, curves 1, 2 and 3). The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were read directly from the graph at \bar{n} values of 0.5 and 1.5 respectively and were found to be 5.67 and 4.92 (at 20°); 5.81 and 5.02 (at 30°), 5.91 and 5.12 (at 40°) respectively. These values of successive stability constants were further refined by the following methods:

- (1) Convergence formulas of successive approximations¹⁴
- (2) Correction term method¹⁵
- (3) Least Square treatment¹⁵

and shown in Table I.

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TABLE I

Method	20°			30°			40°		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β
Schroder's convergence formulas	5.40	5.19	10.59	5.54	5.29	10.83	5.62	5.41	11.03
Correction term	5.32	5.28	10.60	5.40	5.32	10.72	5.58	5.38	10.96
Least Square	5.47	5.09	10.56	5.53	5.14	10.67	5.58	5.23	10.81
Mean	5.39	5.19	10.58	5.49	5.25	10.74	5.59	5.34	10.93

Thermodynamic Functions : The values of the overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) on complex formation have been determined at 30°. The expression¹⁶

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln \beta \quad (15)$$

relating overall stability constant β to the total free energy change of the reaction was employed for evaluating the value of ΔG , which was found to be -14.87 K-cal/mole.

The value of ΔH was determined with the help of an isobar¹⁶ equation given as follows

$$d \ln \beta / dT = \Delta H / RT^2 \quad (16)$$

where T is the absolute temperature and R is the gas constant and may be conveniently written in the form

$$d \log \beta / d(1/T) = \Delta H / 4.57 \quad (17)$$

The mean value of $\log \beta$ (from Table-I) obtained at different temperatures were plotted as a function of $(1/T)$. The gradient of the tangent drawn at the point corresponding to 30° was determined and equated with $-\Delta H/4.57$ ¹⁶. The value of ΔH thus obtained was found to be -7.03 K-cal/mole.

The overall entropy change (ΔS) of the reaction was calculated from the equation¹⁶ $\Delta S = (\Delta H - \Delta G)/T$ and found to be $+25.87$ cal/deg.

The present investigation clearly reveals the formation of two complex species, NiSA and Ni(SA)₂²⁻. The logarithms of the successive stability constants were found to be 5.39 ± 0.07 and 5.19 ± 0.10 (at 20°), 5.49 ± 0.09 and 5.25 ± 0.11 (at 30°); and 5.59 ± 0.03 and 5.34 ± 0.11 (at 40°) respectively. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS evaluated at 30° were found to be -14.87 K-cal/mole, -7.03 K-cal/mole and $+25.87$ cal/deg. respectively.

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